

DiSSCo Transition Project

**Report on state of standards
interoperability and gap analysis for next
stage of DiSSCo RI development**

Work Package 4 - Deliverable 4.1

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Executive Summary

This report provides an overview of the current status of data standards interoperability within the DiSSCo (Distributed System of Scientific Collections) infrastructure and identifies critical gaps and development priorities as DiSSCo progresses from the Transition phase to the Construction phase.. It evaluates the advancement and provides updates on the implementation status of fundamental standards such as [Latimer Core](#), [MIDS](#) (Minimum Information about a Digital Specimen), and [openDS](#) (Open Digital Specimen), while examining their contributions to collection-level descriptions, digitisation tracking, and machine-actionable specimen data. The research additionally addresses the obstacles to standards adoption, encompassing institutional constraints, deficiencies in tools, and dependence on a limited expert group for development initiatives.

Drawing on pilot implementations, collaborations with international partners (e.g. [GBIF](#), [CETAF](#), [TDWG](#)), and community feedback, this report identifies key areas for continued development to ensure DiSSCo's success. These include:

- Improving interoperability between systems and standards used across institutions and national nodes
- Enhancing scalability to support the growing volume and complexity of data within DiSSCo services
- Ensuring long-term sustainability through stable governance, support, and technical maintenance
- Refining and aligning data standards (e.g. Latimer Core, openDS, MIDS) to evolving infrastructure needs
- Formalising key policies and service models, including those for data stewardship, identifiers, and access services
- Investing in tooling and shared infrastructure, such as schema validation tools, packaging pipelines, and annotation services
- Developing and adopting controlled vocabularies to ensure consistent metadata and machine-readability

These priorities are essential to support [FAIR](#) (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data practices across European natural science collections and to position DiSSCo as a fully integrated part of the global biodiversity data ecosystem.

Keywords: Digital specimens, Biodiversity informatics, Data standards, FAIR data, Persistent identifiers, openDS, Latimer Core, MIDS (Minimum Information about a Digital Specimen), Taxon Concept Standard (TCS), Natural science collections

1. Introduction

Globally, there is growing momentum around data aggregation, sharing, and collaboration as essential responses to the biodiversity and climate crises. Initiatives such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility ([GBIF](#)), the Ocean Biodiversity Information System ([OBIS](#)), the Long-Term Ecological Research network ([LTER](#)), the Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network ([GEO BON](#)) and the Biodiversity Heritage Library ([BHL](#)) exemplify efforts to make biodiversity data openly accessible and interoperable across national and institutional boundaries. These global infrastructures depend heavily on standardised data and collaborative frameworks to mobilise vast quantities of biodiversity information, enabling cross-disciplinary research and policy development. Frameworks like the Convention on Biological Diversity ([CBD](#)) and its associated targets, including those under the [Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework](#), increasingly call for harmonised, transparent data to monitor and guide global biodiversity commitments. As such, there is a strong international driver for aligning data infrastructures to facilitate more effective biodiversity monitoring, forecasting, and sustainable management. This global landscape reinforces the need for national and regional initiatives like DiSSCo to integrate with broader efforts, contributing to a federated ecosystem of interoperable biodiversity data platforms. This has been addressed on European level through the creation of the Biodiversity Community Integrated Knowledge Library ([BICIKL](#)) project in which DiSSCo, eLTER, LifeWatch and GBIF and other partners closely worked together to establish bi-directional links and a joint [Biodiversity Knowledge Hub](#) with a FAIR Data Place for exchanging data.

Biodiversity data standards have played an essential role in the development of global research infrastructures, supporting policy making, data integration, interoperability and long-term accessibility (Heberling et al, 2021). The first iteration of [Darwin Core](#) - one of the mostly widely adopted biodiversity data standards - first emerged in the late 1990s, and set the foundation for structured species occurrence data sharing (Wieczorek et al, 2012). Supported by other standards like [ABCD](#) (Access to Biological Collections Data) and its extension, [EFG](#) (Extension for Geosciences), these standards have been crucial in the digitisation, aggregation and utility of biodiversity data (Petersen et al, 2018).

1.1 Data Standards in DiSSCo

At the time of the DiSSCo Transition Project (DTP) grant submission, there were clear and well-documented gaps in data standards required to support DiSSCo's ambition to deliver a unified, [FAIR](#)-compliant infrastructure for natural science collections (Koureas et al, 2024). While core community standards such as Darwin Core and ABCD were foundational to data sharing, they did not fully support the breadth or complexity of data required by DiSSCo services. This included gaps in collection-level metadata (addressed by the emerging Latimer Core standard), granularity of digitisation progress (addressed by MIDS), and the need for a structured, machine-actionable representation of a Digital Specimen (addressed by the Open Digital Specimen specification, openDS).

DiSSCo, as envisioned in its Design Blueprint (Hardisty et al, 2020), represents a paradigm shift in how European natural science collections are managed, shared and accessed. DiSSCo has the goal to unify disparate collections into a single, digitally accessible European research infrastructure, ensuring that biodiversity data is FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This effort is driven by a recognition that high-quality, standardised data is essential to solving global biodiversity challenges, supporting research, policy-making, and conservation strategies at an unprecedented scale - adopting, developing and promoting the use of standards is key.

While this report focuses primarily on physical and digital specimen data and associated collection-level information, it is important to note that natural science collections also encompass a range of other data types. These include molecular and genomic data, geochemical and isotopic datasets, and media-rich content such as audio and video recordings. Although these data types fall outside the core scope of this deliverable, they present important future challenges for standards alignment and interoperability. As DiSSCo evolves, its infrastructure will need to account for the integration and referencing of these data types, ensuring that linkages between physical specimens and derived or associated data are preserved in a coherent and scalable way.

2. Data Standards

At the beginning of the DiSSCo Transition Project (DTP), the need to strengthen data interoperability across the European natural science collections community was well recognised, but the standards ecosystem remained fragmented and incomplete. Latimer Core was in its final stages of development, with expert review completed and ratification by TDWG pending. It aimed to address long-standing gaps in how collection-level metadata was captured and structured. MIDS (Minimum Information about a Digital Specimen) had been applied in various national initiatives as a way to assess digitisation progress, but it lacked a robust, standardised method for score calculation, resulting in inconsistent and often non-reproducible outputs.

The need for openDS (Open Digital Specimen) became increasingly clear as DiSSCo's infrastructure ambitions matured. Existing standards, while widely adopted, did not adequately support key infrastructure requirements such as versioning, persistent identifiers (PIDs), semantic interoperability, and machine-actionable provenance. These limitations became more pronounced as new use cases emerged, including large-scale digitised media, AI-assisted annotations, and integration with computational workflows. openDS was conceived to fill these gaps by defining a lightweight, structured, and extensible data specification that could serve as the backbone for DiSSCo's digital specimen infrastructure. Its development drew on international collaborations, prior architectural work from projects like DiSSCo Prepare, and alignment with emerging efforts such as the GBIF Unified Data Model, Darwin Core Data Package and TDWG's attribution metadata recommendations.

Together, these standards, Latimer Core, MIDS, openDS, and TCS, form the foundational infrastructure required to realise DiSSCo's ambition of a fully FAIR and semantically rich digital ecosystem for natural science collections. The following sections explore their development, implementation, and integration efforts within DTP, provide a brief overview of geo-collections and other related standards, and outline the remaining work needed to prepare them for production deployment in the DiSSCo Construct phase.

2.1 Latimer Core

2.1.1 Introduction

[Latimer Core](#) (LtC) is a TDWG data standard designed for describing collections rather than individual specimens or objects. In contrast to specimen-level standards such as Darwin Core and ABCD,, Latimer Core focuses on representing groups of objects. The granularity of these groups can vary widely depending on the use case, ranging from the contents of a single drawer to an institution's entire holdings.

This approach is particularly useful in cases (currently representing the majority of global natural science collections) where specimen-level digitisation has not yet been completed, providing institutions a mechanism for describing and quantifying their collections without complete digitisation. Latimer Core is also intended to support a range of additional use cases, including the creation of thematic collections and the integration of rich textual narratives for historic or notable collections. Additionally, it provides structured approaches to modelling the often complex relationships between different collections, and how those relationships (and collections) change and develop over time.

Latimer Core consists of 25 classes (summarised in Fig. 1 below), with the core concept of a group of collection objects enshrined as the `ObjectGroup` class (defined as "an intentionally grouped set of objects with one or more common characteristics.").

Fig. 1: Summary of Latimer Core classes (source: Woodburn et al., 2022)

2.1.2 Background

At the start of DiSSCo Transition, the development of Latimer Core was largely complete. While still officially in a draft state, the standard terms and definitions were finished, and the TDWG independent expert review had been successfully completed. Latimer Core's [normative documentation](#) and [non-normative guidance](#), and the standard had been recommended by the TDWG Executive Committee to proceed to public review. See TDWG processes for more information about the procedural framework for developing and ratifying standards (<https://www.tdwg.org/about/process/>).

In terms of application and adoption of Latimer Core prior to its formal ratification:

- GBIF indicated plans to adopt Latimer Core in its roadmap for the Global Registry of Scientific Collections ([GRSciColl](#))
- CETAF expressed intentions to align the [CETAF Registry of Collections](#) with Latimer Core.
- DiSSCo planned to use Latimer Core for:
 - Storing collection-level data in the DiSSCo core architecture.
 - Supporting services such as ELViS (European Loans and Visits System).
- Preliminary discussions were held with the TDWG Task Group on implementation, though most initiatives were paused pending formal ratification of the standard.

Various reference examples of the use of Latimer Core had been created and published in the TDWG Task Group's GitHub repository, but at this point the most substantive application of the draft standard was carried out by DiSSCo Flanders, who used Latimer Core for their survey of Flemish collections, including developing a Latimer Core-based database schema to structure the data. A report of this work was published using the TDWG Implementation Experience Report format (Breugelmans and Trekels, 2023)).

Latimer Core shares conceptual overlaps and alignments with several other standards. These include fundamental data concepts from [Dublin Core](#), specimen-related information found in [Darwin Core](#) and its extensions, [ABCD](#) (including [EFG](#), the geosciences extension), and the [CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model](#). It also intersects with the [W3C PROV](#) provenance ontology in areas related to people, activities, and attribution, and overlaps with the [W3C ORG ontology](#) in representing organisations and organisational units. Some generic definitions, such as those for addresses and contact details, have also been adapted from Schema.org. This alignment creates opportunities for adopters to use Latimer Core alongside other standards. For instance, while Latimer Core includes a basic representation of organisational units, users may choose to substitute it with the more comprehensive W3C ORG ontology where appropriate.

The development approach has primarily involved adopting existing terms from other standards, particularly Darwin Core, rather than creating new definitions. Additionally, related terms and aligned concepts have been identified to follow best practices and enhance interoperability between standards. One useful method, suggested by a reviewer, has been the use of the [SKOS mapping properties](#) to define relationships between Latimer Core terms and corresponding terms in other standards. This approach provides a foundation that can be expanded over time.

2.1.3 Current Status

After successfully completing public review, Latimer Core achieved formal ratification as a TDWG standard in February 2024. In the same year, the Latimer Core Maintenance Group was formed under the parent Collections Description Interest Group for the purposes of maintaining the newly ratified Latimer Core schema. The Collections Description Interest Group is the parent of both the Latimer Core Maintenance Group and Minimum Information about a Digital Specimen Task Group.

Latimer Core has now also achieved a first application in a production infrastructure, in the implementation by GRSciColl of Latimer Core API endpoints for [collections](#) and [institutions](#).

Assistance was provided to the GBIF in mapping the existing GRSciColl schema to terms defined within the Latimer Core standard. This collaborative effort contributed to the alignment of data models and supported broader interoperability goals within the collections community.

To demonstrate the utility and application of Latimer Core, a prototype platform was developed using [Airtable](#) (a spreadsheet-database hybrid cloud platform). This platform allowed prospective users to explore the standard in a relational, tabular format, offering a practical environment in which to:

- Experiment with the creation of Latimer Core schemes for a variety of use cases;
- Explore example datasets in pursuit of assessing their own

- Gain insight into presentation of Latimer Core to end users

Additionally, a generic script, published via Google Colab, was developed to enable the extraction of data from Airtable in a Latimer Core-compliant JSON format. This tool supports downstream integration and data exchange.

To support community engagement and capacity building, a familiarisation and training workshop was delivered at the 2024 Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) conference, using the Airtable demonstrator as a hands-on resource (Livermore et al, 2024). Pilot activities were also undertaken at the Natural History Museum (NHM), London, where Latimer Core was trialled using Airtable to support the planning and monitoring of digitisation projects.

Finally, Latimer Core profiles were developed in JSON Schema format for use in the DiSSCo EU Collections Digitisation Dashboard. These profiles were derived from data originally collected during the proof-of-concept phase of the Dashboard, which was initiated under the SYNTHESYS+ project (Smith et al, 2019).

2.1.4 Further work after DTP

- Map the national [DiSSCo UK](#) collections survey data to the Latimer Core schema as a use case.
- Consider creating a proof of concept of LtC-brokered interoperability between the DiSSCo UK collections survey data and the [DiSSCo Flanders](#) Flemish collections survey data.
- Map and align the CETAF Registry of Collections data structure to Latimer Core.
- Complete Latimer Core alignment for collections components of the DiSSCo EU core data architecture and the ELViS data model.
- Pilot interoperability between DiSSCo EU collection-level data and GRSciColl.
- Develop controlled vocabularies for key terms (e.g. ltc:Discipline) across DiSSCo services.
- Maintain an active DiSSCo presence in the TDWG Latimer Core Maintenance Group, and report implementation experiences and challenges back to TDWG with a view to refining the standard through TDWG processes.
- Explore the use of [Grist](#) as a demonstration and production platform for managing Latimer Core datasets.
- Work with the TDWG Standards Interoperability Interest Group on continuing to map and improve interoperability between Latimer Core and other standards, based on the [SSSOM framework](#).

2.2 Minimum Information about Digital Specimens (MIDS)

2.2.1 Introduction

The digitisation of natural science collections involves converting analogue information about physical specimens, such as labels, images, and contextual metadata, into digital

formats. However, the term "digitisation" is used inconsistently across institutions and projects, often reflecting local goals, resources, and practices. This variation makes it difficult to assess or compare the extent and quality of digitisation, either within a single institution or across collections.

To address this, the Minimum Information about a Digital Specimen (MIDS) specification was developed under the Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) framework. MIDS defines a tiered framework for assessing and reporting the completeness of digital specimen data, offering a structured way to monitor progress, set priorities, and support data-driven decision making in digitisation programmes.

MIDS is a minimum specification, meaning that it defines the essential data expected at each digitisation level but does not preclude capturing more. The framework focuses on whether key information elements are present, rather than the accuracy or quality of those elements. This makes MIDS particularly useful for:

- Comparing digitisation progress between institutions or projects
- Informing funding or policy decisions
- Supporting prioritisation in digitisation workflows
- Enabling automated, reproducible assessment of data completeness

The specification includes four MIDS levels (plus a pre-digitisation "Level 0"), each reflecting a stage in the digitisation process:

- MIDS 0 (Bare): A minimal digital link to a physical specimen, enabling basic referencing
- MIDS 1 (Basic): Discovery-level data and usage permissions
- MIDS 2 (Intermediate): Core scientific metadata typically required for research use
- MIDS 3 (Extended): Rich metadata enabling integration with other datasets and systems

2.2.2 Background

In 2020, the MIDS Task Group was formed to develop a standard for Minimum Information about a Digital Specimen. The need for the standard had been highlighted during the ICEDIG project (European Commission, 2020) and work on it had already commenced both under the banner of that project and with contributions by the members of the CETAF Digitisation Working Group. ICEDIG ended in early 2020. In July of that year, a draft definition and specification was released on GitHub. Work on the standard continued throughout 2021 and 2022. In the meantime, diverse specifications of MIDS were interpreted and adapted from the draft definitions for several practical use cases, such as collection inventories performed in DiSSCo UK, DiSSCo Flanders and design of a collection digitisation dashboard in the SYNTHESIS+ projects. These MIDS assessments had no formal methodology and relied heavily on guesstimates by collection managers, rather than raw data, rendering them time-consuming, potentially unreliable and difficult to reproduce.

In 2022, an R-Shiny app was created at Meise Botanic Garden to calculate MIDS scores at the specimen level for a GBIF-produced Darwin Core Archive, called the [MIDSCalculator](#). This tool was designed to calculate the MIDS scores based on a mapping logic of Darwin Core terms specified in a JSON schema, combined with a few implicit assumptions hardcoded in the app. The tool's capabilities were presented at the SPNHC and TDWG annual conferences in 2022 (Dillen et al, 2022), but this did not lead to significant uptake.

In the course of 2023, the contents of each MIDS level were thoroughly reviewed by the members of the task group, leading to an informally agreed upon set of information elements sorted into the different MIDS level categories by the end of that year, when DiSSCo Transition started (December 2023).

At this point, there was still no up-to-date clear documentation covering the work of the previous few years, no formal method to calculate MIDS scores other than the ad hoc and incomplete mapping built into the MIDSCalculator app, now out of date, and a MIDS calculating implementation developed by the DiSSCo development team, also based on a preliminary interpretation of the different levels and their elements.

2.2.3 Current Status

In December 2023, work commenced on creating a SSSOM mapping for MIDS. SSSOM is a standard which is intended for easily mapping vocabularies or ontologies to one another (Matentzoglou et al. 2022). It can also be used to map terms to related or identical terms in other standards, such as was done for Latimer Core. In MIDS, the intent was to use SSSOM to map the information elements to one or more terms in other standards, so that MIDS calculation could be performed and reproduced without any ambiguity on datasets structured according to the mapped data standard. By creating these mappings for different data standards, like Darwin Core and ABCD, and for different disciplines, the methodology of calculating MIDS can be formalized.

In the course of 2024 and the DiSSCo Transition runtime, the structure of the SSSOM mapping was updated and refined. The SSSOM approach was also [documented](#) and a walkthrough created how it could be implemented in any third party data management platform. Support was extended to ABCD and metadata for mapping sets was added, facilitating machine readability and versioning of the different mappings.

The MIDSCalculator tool received an overhaul to base its calculation logic on a SSSOM mapping set, rather than the dated JSON schema, and was also modified to be able to support generic Darwin Core archives, not just Occurrence Core files produced by GBIF. Support for ABCD Biocase archives was also included.

Additionally in 2024, a web [tool](#) was created at NHM London using the new SSSOM mappings that was capable of calculating MIDS levels for occurrence datasets on GBIF using GBIF APIs. This tool was in part created to provide a simpler mechanism for non-technical users to get a MIDS calculation for their collections that didn't require

downloading and installing a Shiny app - users can simply visit a [website](#) and calculate their score. The calculations are [more limited](#) than those produced by the aforementioned MIDSCalculator due to a lack of availability of certain data via the GBIF APIs.

Results from these different tools could now be compared to note any discrepancies and identify any issues with the SSSOM pipeline and such analyses were discussed during MIDS task group meetings.

To document the latest developments in MIDS and centralize this information, a draft [website](#) was launched on GitHub pages built directly from the standard's raw data files, including the SSSOM mappings. In the process of generating the site, old data files were cleaned up, terminology refined and harmonized, so that there is now one central place where the standard's scope and elements are documented. This exercise will be of help during the ratification process, which was formally initiated in 2024 and discussed with TDWG's technical architecture group.

A full implementation of all MIDS levels was done in the DiSSCo core infrastructure as part of its deliverable [D3.1](#). For every specimen DiSSCo ingests, it will calculate the MIDS level of the specimen data. This calculation will be rerun on each enhancement of the specimen, allowing it to grow to higher MIDS levels. During DTP, DiSSCo has run tests evaluating the MIDS calculation within DiSSCo with that of the MIDSCalculator tool. The small differences were discussed in the MIDS meeting and implementations were aligned.

Within DiSSCo the calculation of MIDS is coded into the DiSSCo core infrastructure and does not use the new SSSOM mappings. The change to implement the SSSOM mapping will be placed on the backlog of DiSSCo to implement at a later date.

2.2.4 Further work after DTP

- Scale up MIDS calculations. This will be coordinated by the MIDS task group, to aggregate MIDS scores for different datasets and in the process assess the impact of mapping decisions. The MIDS calculation tools now available will be leveraged for this.
- Reach out to infrastructures like GBIF to discuss MIDS implementation in their tools, including the IPT.
- Investigate the potential complementarity of MIDS with the TDWG [Data Quality](#) group. Some of the tests defined in the Data Quality framework, like "NotEmpty" could be referenced and implemented to support attempts in MIDS to avoid false positives. Currently, in the SSSOM mappings, `semav:RegexRemoval` is used for this, but there remain some unresolved issues as this vocabulary suffers from ambiguities in implementation, such as what kind of whitespace is and should be covered. Resolving the issues surrounding unknown and empty values is still scheduled to be addressed in MIDS task group meetings in the course of 2025.
- Draft SSSOM Mappings for the paleontology and geology domains.
- Liaise with the TDWG [Standards Mapping](#) task group to harmonise the usage of SSSOM across all TDWG standards, in particular for MIDS for which the framework has become so important.

- Continue the ratification process of MIDS.
- Ensure future work in DiSSCo-related projects like DiSSCo UK and DiSSCo Flanders 2 uses an up-to-date specification of MIDS and gather feedback from their experiences with practical use of the standard.

2.3 OpenDS

2.3.1 Introduction

Open Digital Specimen (openDS) is a comprehensive data specification that describes the essence of a "Digital Specimen" as implemented by [DiSSCo](#), a digital surrogate of a specimen on the internet with its related information. The openDS data model is based on existing TDWG standards such as [Darwin Core](#), [Audiovisual Core](#), [ABCD](#) and [Chronometric Age](#). It provides a semantic structure for describing the specimen information which is based on the draft of the [GBIF Unified Model](#). openDS is designed to enhance [FAIR aspects](#) of specimen data including support for provenance data and machine actionability.

2.3.2 Background

In the Biodiversity_Next 2019 symposium, a vision of Digital Specimens based on the concept of a Digital Object Architecture, DOA (Kahn and Wilensky 2006) (DOA) was discussed as a new layer to allow applications to interact with information about specimens and collections. This vision required a specification that describes what a Digital Specimen is, and how to technically implement it. This has been further discussed and detailed in a MOBILISE Workshop in Warsaw, 2020, with stakeholders like GBIF, iDigBio, CETAF and DiSSCo (Addink & Hardisty, 2020). With the agreed scope and structure in place, a working group in the DiSSCo Prepare project started on the technical specification of the 'open Digital Specimen' (openDS), see Deliverable 5.3 (Fichtmueller et al, 2023).

Initially the idea was to base the openDS object model on `bco:MaterialSample` in the OBO Foundry's Biological Collection Ontology (BCO), which is linked to Darwin Core and from `iao:InformationContentEntity` in OBO Foundry's Information Artifact Ontology (IAO). While DarwinCore is the primary standard in use for exchange of biodiversity data, it misses the semantic structure required for reasoning over the data and BCO could solve this. This idea was later abandoned by the group, as it was felt that there was little community support for using ontologies and RDF, there were compatibility issues, for example the biodiversity standards community concluded that specimens are material entities rather than material samples (e.g. they often include mounting materials), and BCO was not actively maintained (and by only one person). Also there were new developments towards a TDWG biodiversity standards ontology in alignment with a new GBIF unified data model as result of the Diversifying the GBIF data model project (Wieczorek & Robertson, 2022). The group decided for the time being to go for a specification based on JSON Schema. This does not provide semantic structure in the same way that ontologies, or semantic web technologies (like RDF/OWL) do. However, it does provide a way to define the structural and syntactic constraints of JSON data. By applying Linked Data principles to the JSON Schema, a

lightweight JSON based Linked Data can be created by using [JSON-LD](#). This JSON Linked Data format can be converted into RDF and Turtle files.

Another idea that was developed further was to make use of the RDA/TDWG attribution metadata recommendation (using Prov-O ontology) for provenance. Provenance data is not supported by the TDWG biodiversity standards but needed to record changes in digital specimen data and attribute the agents that make these changes. openDS was developed using JSON Schema, but has been designed for compatibility with the attribution metadata.

The group created a DiSSCo Modelling Framework (DMF) using Wikibase/Mediawiki software. The DMF was set up to model the terms of the DiSSCo Digital Specimen Object Specification. The idea was that the DiSSCo community could collaboratively do the modelling in DMF and pipelines would then export the data model and convert it for future reference into a JSON Schema. This schema would then be used for the automated processing and validation of specimen data by the DiSSCo infrastructure and to generate human readable documentation of the terms that make up openDS. A prototypical export script was created for this purpose that queried the DMF SPARQL endpoint, parsed the response and transformed this into a JSON Schema definition that could be included in a processing service for data processing and validation. JSON schema was chosen as it was decided to use JSON as the primary data format in DiSSCo.

2.3.3 Current status

In DTP the experimental DMF was abandoned as an active community of volunteers to do the modelling work could not be established and it was creating too much overhead for developing the JSON schemas. DMF could in principle be resurrected once a user base for openDS has been established and an active community willing to contribute to openDS modelling exists. The openDS data model was further developed by Naturalis by further developing the JSON schemas into version 0.4 (and the FDO profiles into v1.0). These schemas can be found at <https://schemas.dissco.tech/>. A route to auto-generate documentation based on the schemas was further developed using a solution developed by NHM for documenting the Latimer Core standard, created by Ben Norton. This resulted in documentation that is easy to read and has a similar look and feel to existing TDWG biodiversity standards documentation. This documentation is available at <https://terms.dissco.tech>. Because it is auto-generated it is never out of date or out of sync.

While version 0.4 may be extended by additional terms in the future, it is seen as sufficiently mature and having all the structure in place to support a minimum viable product of the DiSSCo core data infrastructure. This version was community reviewed in DTP by global stakeholders in TDWG Biodiversity Standards, the International Partners for the Digital Extended Specimen and by DiSSCo partners. Feedback was collected and discussed through [github issues](#). The version was implemented in the MVP (see D3.1), except for the specimen parts section, and includes support for Earth Science and extraterrestrial specimens (e.g. meteorites).

Features of openDS 0.4 in a nutshell:

- Supports interoperability with existing standards by reusing (or “borrowing”) terms from Darwin Core and other established standards
- Provides structure and context to data and is presented as JSON
- Supports both biological and earth science specimens
- Supports provenance data, annotations and versioning
- Optimized for machine actionability through support for PIDs and FDO profiles
- Support extension of specimen data through entity-relationships and assertions

2.3.4 Further work after DTP

The openDS specification will need to be maintained and further developed for compatibility with new developments in TDWG biodiversity standards. The specification includes terms and classes for which data cannot yet be shared through existing DwC and ABCD standards. GBIF has a similar issue with the unified model. A new exchange format is under development called DarwinCore Data Package, based on the Frictionless Data format that should make this possible, and DiSSCo should support this format when it becomes available. Also continued effort is needed to align openDS with the evolving GBIF unified model to support publication of openDS data in GBIF.

When the DarwinCore Mineralogy extension becomes available, openDS should be updated to support the new terms in this extension.

DarwinCore currently is missing a term to include the digital specimen DOI or a Discipline term to state the topic of a specimen. New terms for this have been proposed and further work may be needed after DTP to get these accepted into DarwinCore. Being able to include the digital specimen DOI in DarwinCore datasets will reduce the risk of creating duplicate digital specimens (which can at the moment only be related to a DwC record through a physical specimen identifier, that may change over time), and also make it possible for stakeholders like GBIF and Pensoft to include the DOIs in their tools and infrastructures.

2.4 Geo-Collections Standards

As of November 2024, CETAF is preparing a case study-based publication focused on enhancing the quality, discoverability, and usability of Earth Science collection data by aligning them with FAIR principles, ensuring they are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. The purpose of this paper is to provide a comprehensive desk study that addresses challenges in data interoperability and proposes practical solutions for improvement. It will include detailed case studies of Earth Science specimens that demonstrate both their research and societal value, along with an analysis of the metadata needed to increase their discoverability.

The publication will examine existing metadata standards, identify current gaps, and offer actionable recommendations for adapting these standards and the data model

specifically for the GeoCASE system. It will also provide clear guidance on which controlled vocabularies and terms should be used when completing these standards. Furthermore, it will propose data workflows and best-practice guidelines to enhance specimen data pipelines. Overall, this structured approach is designed to support institutions in improving data quality and to underscore the critical role of geological collections in tackling global scientific and societal challenges, ultimately aiming to make a significant impact academically, societally, and in terms of research funding.

In 2024, CETAF ESG began compiling best-practice controlled vocabularies to standardise metadata across institutions. These include:

- Mineralogy: Dana, Nickel-Strunz, Mindat-Strunz, and the International Mineralogical Association (IMA) nomenclature.
- Petrology: IUGS classification for igneous and metamorphic rocks, BGS rock classification schemes.
- Stratigraphy: International Chronostratigraphic Chart, Geologic Timescales (2020).
- Palaeontology: Taxonomic name registries (Paleobiology Database, WoRMS, Catalogue of Life).

In 2022, the formation of the Mineralogy Extension Task Group was motivated by the need to extend the support of the Darwin Core Archive and TDWG community to Mineralogy and as a first step in a larger effort to extend the entire TDWG community to Earth Sciences. The primary goal of the task group was to generate a list of terms and definitions that would extend Darwin Core to mineralogy. In early 2025, this goal was accomplished with the release of a preliminary set of terms and definitions (<https://tdwg.github.io/mineralogy>) with ratification planned for August 2025. The Mineralogy Extension is the first extension specifically designed to support both the existing Darwin Core standard and the upcoming Darwin Core Data Package, planned for release in September of 2025.

2.5 TCS

The [Taxon Concept Standard \(TCS\)](#) is the TDWG standard for sharing taxonomic data. However, TCS is an XML schema, making it unsuitable for sharing data in formats other than XML. This imposes a strict requirement and limits its usability.

In contrast, the Darwin Core (DwC) standard, which has seen much wider adoption, includes a Taxon class well-suited for providing data about taxon identifications. However, although commonly used for that purpose (Wieczorek et al., 2012), it is less effective for handling classification data, as required by Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), Catalogue of Life (CoL), and similar initiatives. Unlike DwC's Taxon class, the Taxon Concept in TCS includes not only a taxon name but also a description of a taxon, referred to as "accordingTo" in the standard. Since the same name can be applied to different taxonomic groups, defining the circumscription of the taxonomic group is crucial.

To facilitate broader adoption of TCS, the TCS 2 Task Group, formed in 2021, has been working on a major revision (Klazenga and Liljebblad, 2024). This new version aims to move TCS away from its XML schema and transform it into a vocabulary standard of terms and definitions (a [W3C SKOS concept](#)), maintained under the [TDWG Vocabulary Maintenance Standard](#). The updated version, [TCS 2](#), is nearing public review.

TCS originally included the *CharacterCircumscription* and *SpecimenCircumscription* elements, which have not yet been incorporated into TCS 2. With the increasing number of molecular sequence-based classifications being published to accommodate dark taxa — organisms known only from eDNA data — the TCS 2 Task Group and UTartu, as part of the DiSSCo Transition Project, have been exploring ways to accommodate DNA-based taxon hypotheses, particularly for taxa that lack formally described names, while also linking them to established taxonomic classifications such as CoL.

As part of an example implementation of [TCS applied to UNITE Taxon Hypotheses](#), the UTartu team identified two key issues related to DNA-based taxon hypotheses. We propose these issues for discussion and potential inclusion in the updated version of TCS:

1. *tcs:taxonRank*. TCS 2 recommends using a controlled vocabulary such as [GBIF's Taxonomic Rank Vocabulary](#) for the *taxonRank* property. However, the Dwc's *verbatimTaxonRank* property allows the use of taxonomic rank designations not included in a controlled vocabulary. From the perspective of DNA-based taxon hypotheses, it would be beneficial to allow ranks that reflect methodology used to calculate taxon hypotheses, such as genetic distance or clustering threshold. One potential solution is to incorporate distance values and clustering thresholds into the *verbatimTaxonRank* field, linking them to the methodology-associated metric.
2. Taxonomic circumscriptions. The original TCS circumscription elements were omitted from TCS 2 because their intended use was not immediately clear to Task Group members. The plan is to incorporate circumscriptions into TCS 2 at a later stage as part of a separate effort, ensuring they are operational and computationally tractable. For DNA-based taxon hypotheses, defining taxonomic circumscriptions — such as sequence and specimen identifiers — within a taxon concept is essential. We propose an initial structure for specimen- and sequence-based circumscriptions, based on Digital Specimen Identifiers and INSDC sequence accession numbers. A Digital Specimen Identifier (*digitalSpecimenID*) is a persistent, FAIR Digital Object-compliant identifier for a Digital Specimen digital object on the internet. This is a new term proposed for Darwin Core by the DiSSCo Technical Team.

One of the challenges in working with taxonomic data is that we are often dealing with incomplete data. By using taxon concepts rather than just taxon names, and incorporating expert knowledge through taxon concept mappings in datasets and name resolution, we can take meaningful steps toward addressing this issue. The transition from TCS 1 to TCS 2 represents a major step forward in making the Taxon Concept Standard more versatile and accessible beyond XML. The proposed changes aim to ensure that TCS 2 can effectively

accommodate DNA-based taxon hypotheses while maintaining compatibility with existing classification frameworks.

2.6 Other Standards-related Work

2.6.1 International Image Interoperability Framework - IIIF

DiSSCo supports remote image servers that store images using the [IIIF standard](#). DiSSCover uses OpenSeadragon to display an interactive image viewer on the digital media page. This viewer both supports the regular image types and IIIF standard. Users can freely move around the image and zoom in and out. It uses Annotorious 3.0 to draw visual elements upon images for annotation purposes, which supports both regular image formats and IIIF.

The IIIF manifests can also be accessed through the DiSSCo Digital Media object but the IIIF metadata is not included directly in the digital media object. DiSSCo also does not currently support conversion from IIIF annotations into the DiSSCo annotations framework. Since both IIIF and DiSSCo are using the Web Annotation Model, this seems feasible for the future, for example by creating a dedicated Machine Annotation Service that does this conversion. DiSSCo has not provided guidelines on manifests and may need to do so in the future to further harmonize the image metadata (in the Construct phase).

2.6.2 W3C Web Annotation Data Model

DiSSCo has followed the Web Annotation Data Model for its Annotation digital objects. However the annotations annotate sections of the JSON object rather than HTML elements in a HTML page, and in media objects regions of interest (media fragments) are annotated. Following the W3C model. The annotation object contains besides the annotation itself also metadata about which object is annotated, what part of the object, who made the annotation and when.

DiSSCo uses the motivations Commenting, Editing and Assessing as defined in the W3C model, but adds custom motivations for Adding and Deleting. The W3C model supports this. The DiSSCo implementation has not been tested for interoperability with other annotation platforms; this may be needed in the future to integrate annotations from other platforms than DiSSCover.

2.6.3 Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)

Support for persistent identifiers in openDS goes beyond current community standards such as Darwin Core and Latimer Core. openDS contains extra metadata describing a PID to support machine actionability like GUPRI Level and identifier status (preferred, alternative or superseded identifier). GUPRI Level is an indicator for how persistent an identifier is, it tells whether an identifier is Globally Unique or only locally unique, Persistent or only stable and Resolvable or not resolvable. These extra metadata terms

could also be added to the mentioned community standards to improve exchange of information about PIDs.

PIDs in DiSSCo are implemented as DOIs and Handles: a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) is a globally unique, persistent identifier used to reference digital objects, such as specimens or datasets, and is managed through the DOI system (e.g., via DataCite). A Handle is a broader type of persistent identifier from the Handle System, which underlies DOIs but can also be used independently to provide long-term access to digital resources. In DiSSCo's infrastructure, Digital Specimens and Digital Media are assigned PIDs, while other digital objects only get Handles. DOIs are also Handles but guaranteed to be persistent by the DOI Foundation members and resolvable through the doi.org proxy. The implementation of DOIs in DiSSCo is special as it is optimized for machine actionability and open science. It supports some functionality of Handles that is not commonly seen in DOIs:

- Kernel metadata is stored directly in the Handle record so it is always available even if the object itself or DiSSCo no longer exists, and it can be accessed by machines without having to access the full data object.
- Multiple redirect is supported, the DOI redirects to a html landing page by default but also redirects to a machine readable version of the digital object and to a online catalog record from the specimen host if it exists.
- Versioning is supported by appending the version number to the DOI, so the DOI can be used to redirect to the latest version (default) or a specific version of the digital object.

A publication on Digital Specimens is needed which includes PIDs and the implementation on Digital Specimens as done in DiSSCo. This should include a good technical definition to enable other infrastructures to support the same Digital Specimen and PID implementation.

DiSSCo has the ambition to provide DOIs globally through DataCite. Following the DataCite rules this means it needs to administer the landing page for all these DOIs but there are resourcing and cost limitations that need to be considered. An option that could be worked out is to support only static landing pages with minimal metadata rather than full Digital Specimens as versioned objects with annotations.

2.6.4 Controlled vocabularies

DiSSCo needs controlled terms and vocabularies to harmonize the specimen data, improve quality and to foster machine actionability. While the terms have been described in openDS documentation (<https://terms.dissco.tech>), some of these terms could not be borrowed from existing standards and are defined in the ODS namespace. Terms in this namespace do not resolve yet to their definitions however, for this a vocabulary server would be needed. This would enhance machine actionability. During DTP a [vocabulary implementation plan](#) was created, but not yet implemented, as this went beyond the Minimum Viable Product implementation of the Core Infrastructure (see also D3.1). Besides

implementation of a vocabulary server to host DiSSCo vocabularies, several things are needed in the construction phase:

- Descriptive metadata and standardisation across the DiSSCo Nodes through creation and adoption of controlled vocabularies. This is challenging not only because it needs community consensus and changes in local systems but also because Darwin Core, currently used as the primary exchange format in the community, is not suitable for proposing/implementing controlled vocabularies. A new exchange format based on the Frictionless Data Package format called Darwin Core Data Packages which is currently under development by GBIF and TDWG may help as it allows a more semantic description of the data.
- Discipline to describe the nature of a specimen is implemented in GRSciColl but differs to DiSSCo and within the DiSSCo nodes the topic metadata (including discipline and category/subdiscipline) is also implemented slightly differently. To solve this an updated publication should be created superseding the one made in SYNTHESYS+ as part of the Digitisation Dashboard work.

2.6.5 Adoption of openDS for machine annotations in DiSSCo's DiSSCover service

A major objective of the openDS specification is to foster the mobilization of geo- and biodiversity data (taxonomic determinations, traits, sequences, geolocations) for subsequent reuse in the large simulation and prognosis infrastructures set up in the context of the Common European Data Space framework such as the Green Deal Data Space (Santoro, M., Mazzetti, P, 2023).

In this respect, an e-service for the deep learning-based extraction and quantitative analysis of plant traits was designed and developed within DiSSCo Transition to provide comprehensive specimen-based trait data for major morphological traits such as leaf area (Figure 2). The interplay between DiSSCo's curation and annotation system DiSSCover, a component of DiSSCo's core architecture, and the [DL-service builds on semantic mappings to openDS](#) to represent the assignment of annotations involving plant organ segmentation, scale detection and metadata extraction.

The screenshot shows the DiSSCover web interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home', 'All Specimens', 'About', 'Data Export', and a user profile 'R. Rajendran'. Below the navigation bar, the breadcrumb trail is 'Specimens > SANDBOX/ZST-25V-QB5 > Digital Media > SANDBOX/SOJ-OAX-NV1'. The main title is 'SANDBOX/SOJ-OAX-NV1' with a 'Version 1' dropdown. There are buttons for 'Visual Annotation', 'Stop annotating', and 'Actions'. Below the title, there are tabs for 'Digital Media', 'Metadata', and 'Entity Relationships'. The main content area shows a herbarium scan with a 'plant-organ-segmentation' annotation. The annotation details include a bounding box, class 'leaf', and a list of polygon coordinates. The interface also shows a sidebar with fields for 'Digital Specimen Identifier', 'Title', 'Description', 'Creator', and 'Rights'.

Figure 2: Outcome of the machine annotation pipeline of DiSSCo's curation and annotation service DiSSCover. The result of the processing of a herbarium scan shows detected instances of plant organs, labels and scales (for the quantitative determination of areas). The representation of data employs openDS and imported vocabularies involving the Web Annotation Ontology (OA) and TDWG's Audiovisual Core (AC).

3. Discussion

3.1 Challenges in Standards Implementation and Development

The implementation and development of community-driven data standards continue to face several persistent challenges at multiple levels, ranging from institutional and collections management system (CMS) limitations to broader international coordination issues. While DiSSCo is building a robust technical infrastructure, long-term sustainability depends equally on addressing sociotechnical frictions. Standards, and data models that build on them are shaped by institutional histories, power dynamics, and science cultures. Different institutions maintain legacy systems, adhere to varying operational procedures, and may lack the capacity or incentives to fully align with evolving norms. Moreover, tensions can arise between top-down technical mandates and bottom-up curatorial expertise, especially when standardisation is perceived to marginalise local practices or disciplinary autonomy. It is essential to embed standards and their implementation in a web of social norms, organizational structures, and resource disparities.

Experience from the ratification of Latimer Core and the ongoing ratification of the Minimum Information about a Digital Specimen (MIDS) standard has highlighted the sector's reliance on a small number of voluntary expert contributors. This has exposed a structural vulnerability: only a limited pool of individuals possess the deep expertise required to develop, extend, and maintain complex data models. This constraint hampers both the scalability and sustainability of standards development efforts.

Interoperability with existing CMS platforms remains a significant challenge. Many systems lack the flexibility to integrate emerging standards like Latimer Core or MIDS, impeding the smooth exchange and transformation of data across institutional boundaries. Although the concept of a centralised specimen repository offers a compelling vision for improved interoperability, it does not fully resolve the issue of round-tripping data, ensuring that data can be exchanged, modified, and reliably returned in its original or enriched form.

Resource constraints related to technical and semantic expertise are also evident across the broader collections and digitisation community. This limits not only the pace of implementation but also the sector's capacity to participate in shaping and evolving shared data infrastructures. In this context, we recommend forming an Open Digital Specimen (OpenDS) Interest Group to support coordination and best practice sharing but the timing and structure of such a group require careful consideration to ensure maximum engagement and relevance.

3.2 Tooling Gaps and Implementation Barriers

As the Open Digital Specimen (openDS) specification matures, several tooling gaps and technical challenges remain that could hinder widespread implementation and sustainability. OpenDS, developed by DiSSCo and based on the draft GBIF Unified Model, is designed to provide a structured, [JSON Schema](#)-based representation of specimens, enhancing FAIRness, supporting provenance tracking, and improving machine actionability.

One of the most significant barriers identified is data import and transformation, particularly from institutional Collection Management Systems (CMS). The mapping of CMS data to openDS remains a labour-intensive process, complicated further when dealing with complex specimens, such as those involving multiple species.

Another ongoing gap concerns openDS packaging and data publishing workflows. While there has been discussion around adopting the Frictionless Data framework these pipelines are not yet in place, and there is no mature tooling to support end-to-end data packaging, validation, and publication workflows using openDS. This limits the ability of institutions to reliably prepare, share, and validate their data according to the specification.

Provenance support in openDS, based on the RDA/TDWG attribution metadata recommendation and the PROV-O ontology, is a strength. However, integration of provenance tracking into practical tools and services is still underdeveloped in the biodiversity community. While JSON Schema provides syntactic validation, it lacks the semantic reasoning capabilities of RDF or OWL, and the decision to avoid ontology-based implementations due to limited community support has left a gap in inference and integration capabilities.

Another tooling-related challenge lies in interfacing openDS with evolving GBIF infrastructure and expectations. As GBIF develops its own Unified Model and considers new mechanisms for ingesting complex specimen data, such as the Darwin Core Data Package (DwC-DP), close alignment with these developments is essential. openDS will need to remain adaptable and interoperable as these models progress, particularly as current standards (like Darwin Core) do not yet support critical elements such as persistent identifiers (DOIs) for digital specimens or domain-specific terms like `lct:Discipline`.

Finally, while semantic web technologies such as SPARQL and RDF are acknowledged as potential avenues for enabling more sophisticated querying and reasoning over openDS data, these have not been integrated into the current version of the specification due to earlier community resistance and tooling limitations. This area may warrant renewed exploration as interest in Linked Open Data approaches resurfaces in biodiversity informatics.

It may be beneficial to revisit the possibility of forming an OpenDS Interest Group. Such a group could play a vital role in addressing shared implementation challenges, coordinating tooling development, and facilitating the exchange of institutional best practices. Determining the right timing and structure for this group, possibly in alignment with TDWG activities, will be key to ensuring it gains sufficient engagement and traction.

3.3 DiSSCo's Medium and Longer-term Needs

As DiSSCo transitions into the Construct phase, a number of medium- and long-term priorities must be addressed to ensure the infrastructure is stable, standards-aligned, and production-ready. These needs span the areas of standards development, policy, and operational sustainability.

3.3.1 Data Standards Roadmap

The next 18 months will focus on consolidating and aligning DiSSCo's data standards:

- **Open Digital Specimen (openDS):** Further refinement of openDS and alignment with GBIF's evolving Unified Model and the forthcoming DarwinCore Data Package format.

- Latimer Core: Continued development and piloting for collection-level data descriptions, digitisation planning, and registry alignment, with implementation feedback informing the TDWG standardisation process.
- Interoperability: Strengthening translation between DiSSCo, CETAF, GBIF, and national initiatives (e.g. DiSSCo UK, DiSSCo Flanders), with openDS and Latimer Core playing a central role.

To support long-term infrastructure operations DiSSCo needs to consider:

- Policies: Encompassing data stewardship, identifier management, annotation, versioning, and data governance.
- Community Engagement: Establishing an OpenDS Interest Group to coordinate standard development, implementation support, and alignment with TDWG and other partners.
- Tooling Support: Investment in shared tools for schema validation, data packaging, and provenance tracking to reduce institutional overheads and improve consistency.

4. Glossary

- ABCD - The Access to Biological Collection Data (ABCD) Schema. A standard on specimen and observation data. <https://abcd.tdwg.org>
- BHL - Biodiversity Heritage Library. An international consortium digitising and providing access to natural history literature. <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/>
- CBD - The Convention on Biological Diversity <https://www.cbd.int>
- CETAF - Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities, a DiSSCo partner and network of taxonomic institutions across Europe. <https://cetaf.org/>
- CMS - Collections Management System. Examples used for natural science collections include Arctos, BRAHMS, EarthCape, EMu, Kotka, Specify, and Symbiota.
- Darwin Core - A standard to facilitate the sharing of information about biological diversity. Documented at <https://dwc.tdwg.org> and abbreviated as Dwc.
- DTP - DiSSCo Transition Project. Abridged grant proposal: <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.10.e118241>
- DOI - Digital Object Identifier. A globally unique, persistent identifier used to reference digital objects, such as specimens or datasets, and is managed through the DOI system (e.g., via DataCite).
- Dwc - Abbreviation of Darwin Core.
- EFG - ABCD's Extension for Geosciences. <https://www.tdwg.org/community/esp/efg>
- ELViS - European Loans and Visits System. A prototype DiSSCo system aiming to provide a single access point to European Natural Science Collections.
- FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable - set of principles to optimise the reuse of data. <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>
- GBIF - the Global Biodiversity Information Facility. An international network and data infrastructure funded by the world's governments and aimed at providing

anyone, anywhere, open access to data about all types of life on Earth.

<https://www.gbif.org>

- GRSciColl - the Global Registry of Scientific Collections. A worldwide catalogue of scientific collections managed by GBIF. <https://scientific-collections.gbif.org/>
- GUPRI - Globally Unique, Persistent, Resolvable Identifier
- JSON Schema - A data schema that enables consistent use of the JSON data format. <https://json-schema.org>
- Latimer Core - a data standard for describing collections. <https://ltc.tdwg.org>
- LtC - Abbreviation of Latimer Core
- MIDS - Abbreviation of Minimum Information about a Digital Specimen.
- Minimum Information about a Digital Specimen - a standard to help clarify the levels (depth) of digitisation and the minimum information captured and published at each level <https://www.tdwg.org/community/cd/mids>
- OBIS - Ocean Biodiversity Information System, a global data repository for marine biodiversity. <https://obis.org>
- openDS (Open Digital Specimen) - the core object within the DiSSCo infrastructure. <https://terms.dissco.tech/digital-specimen-terms>
- OWL - Web Ontology Language. A group of knowledge representation languages for writing and describing ontologies. <https://www.w3.org/TR/owl-ref/>
- RDA - The Research Data Alliance. A global research community organisation aiming to build social and technical bridges to support and enable open sharing and re-use of data. <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>
- RDF - Resource Description Framework. A data model for describing and exchanging graph data, and part of semantic web standards. <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>
- SPARQL - SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language. <https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-query/>
- TDWG - Biodiversity Information Standards, originally the Taxonomic Databases Working Group. A non-profit organisation working on open standards for biodiversity data. <https://www.tdwg.org>
- Unified Data Model -
- W3C ORG ontology - W3C's Organization Ontology. <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-org/>
- W3C PROV - W3C's group of standards and documentation on provenance of entities, activities, and people involved in the creation of data and things. <https://www.w3.org/TR/2013/NOTE-prov-overview-20130430/>

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